

Spectrophotometric evaluation of solvent effect on the stability constant of charge transfer complexes of Fe^{III} with 5-sulphosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid[†]

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Manuscript received online 16 January 2013, revised 11 February 2013, accepted 17 February 2013

Abstract : The charge transfer complex (CTC) formed by Fe^{III} with 5-sulphosalicylic acid 5-chlorosalicylic acid were studied using spectrophotometric method in mixed solvent system. Four solvent mixtures were taken having variation in amount of 1,4-dioxane as 5, 10, 15 and 20%. In acid range of pH 1–3, both the ligands formed 1 : 1 complex. A graphical method with computer software program was developed for determination of stability constant and molar absorptivity of 1 : 1 complex at pH 2.35 ± 0.05 and ionic strength 0.1 M, maintained by NaClO₄. This approach gave better value than obtained from graphical method neglecting certain terms to make a linear plot. It was observed that both the value of stability constant as well as molar absorptivity increases with increase in the percentage of 1,4-dioxane in the mixed solvent.

Keywords : Stability constant, molar absorptivity, 5-sulphosalicylic acid, 5-chlorosalicylic acid, charge transfer complex, 1,4-dioxane.

Introduction

The presence of Fe^{III} in the environment causes the formation of several complexes with the natural products, such as humic compounds. Such complexes have been studied both in solution and in solid state^{1–4}. Further Fe^{III} due to its pronounced affinity for ligands containing oxygen forms charge transfer complexes with hydroxy benzoic acids including the 2,6-dihydroxy benzoic acid^{5,6}. Thus, salicylic acid and 5-sulphosalicylic acid have extensively been used as colorimetric reagents⁷ for the determination of Fe^{III}. Since the presence of Fe^{III} in the environmental samples is contributing factor towards the complexation of naturally occurring ligands such as humic compound, the interest towards spectrophotometric studies of charge transfer complex formation between Fe^{III} and ligands containing oxygen atom continues⁶. The solvent plays an important role towards the stability of complex formation. It even affects the value of molar absorptivity of the complex⁸. In recent years, a number of papers have appeared towards the study of binary complexes in different dielectric environment^{9–13} and hence,

the studies on metal-ligand equilibria mixed solvent is gaining importance.

The present work deals with the complexation reaction of Fe^{III} with 5-sulphosalicylic acid (5-SSA) and 5-chlorosalicylic acid (5-Cl-SA) in mixed solvent medium in which 1,4-dioxane in different proportion was used for the study of metal-ligand equilibria.

Results and discussion

Method :

Let us consider the formation of 1 : 1 charge-transfer complex as follows :

The stability constant is given by

$$K = \frac{[ML]}{[M][L]} \quad (2)$$

A number of graphical methods have been developed for the determination of stability constant using spectrophotometric data^{14–20}. However, all these methods give approximate values, as to derive the linear equation one or

[†]This paper was presented in the 49th Annual Convention of Chemists held at Bhopal.

the other parameters have been neglected²¹. McBryde has critically reviewed a number of methods for using spectrophotometric data for the determination of equilibrium constant in solution²². Yves Nievergelt has developed a method for determination of equilibrium constant of 1 : 1 complex in terms of spectrophotometric data²³. Recently a method for determination of stability constant of 1 : 1 complex has been reported in which multivariable regression for calculation of equilibrium concentrations was used²⁴. To overcome these problems a simplified method has been developed which is outlined below.

From the eq. (2), it follows

$$K = \frac{[ML]}{(M^0 - [ML])(L^0 - [ML])} \quad (3)$$

where M^0 and L^0 are the analytical concentrations of metal ion and ligand respectively. Charges are omitted for the simplification. If metal ion, ligand and complex absorb light in the region of study, the absorbance per unit path can be expressed as

$$A = (M^0 - [ML]) \epsilon_M + [ML] \epsilon_{ML} + (L^0 - [ML]) \epsilon_L \quad (4)$$

where ϵ_M , ϵ_{ML} and ϵ_L are the molar absorptivity of the species M, ML and L respectively.

The eq. (3) can be rearranged as

$$[ML]^2 - (M^0 + L^0 + 1/K) ML + M^0 L^0 = 0 \quad (5)$$

From which it follows

$$[ML] = \frac{[M^0 L^0]/[M^0 + L^0 + 1/K] + [M^0 L^0]^2/}{[M^0 + L^0 + 1/K]^3 + \dots} \quad (6)$$

If A is the absorbance of the solution under study and the metal ion and ligand does not absorb light then for 1 cm path length one can write

$$A = \epsilon_{ML} [ML] \quad (7)$$

If the higher terms in the eq. (6) were neglected then

$$A = \epsilon_{ML} M^0 L^0 / [M^0 + L^0 + 1/K] \quad (8)$$

Eq. (8) on rearrangement reduces to

$$M^0 L^0 / A = (M^0 + L^0) / \epsilon_{ML} + 1 / \epsilon_{ML} K \quad (9)$$

If $(M^0 L^0) / A$ is plotted against $(M^0 + L^0)$ a straight line with slope $1 / \epsilon_{ML}$ and intercept $1 / \epsilon_{ML} K$ would be obtained.

However if we do not neglect the higher terms then

we get the equation

$$\frac{M^0 L^0}{A} + \frac{A}{\epsilon_{ML}^2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_{ML}} (M^0 + L^0) + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{ML} K} \quad (10)$$

To calculate stability constant and molar absorptivity simultaneously, a novel graphical method with a computer software program was developed. Initially the value of ϵ_{ML} was not known and hence a trial value of ϵ_{ML} was taken as 1.0×10^4 and the left hand side of eq. (10) was plotted against $(M^0 + L^0)$ which results in a straight line. From the slope of this straight line a new value of ϵ_{ML} was obtained, which was refined by successive approximations. The process of computation through iteration was continued till trial value and calculated value became same.

This method provided more accurate and precise value of said parameters. The stability constant and molar absorptivity obtained using the developed graphical-cum-computational method was compared with Frank and Ostwald's method (8) in which the eq. (9) was used. It was observed that the stability constant and molar absorptivity determined from the method developed here are better than the values obtained from the method of Frank and Ostwald. The process was used for determining the stability constant and molar absorptivity in the solution with different proportion of 1,4-dioxane (Tables 1 and 2).

The molar absorptivity depends on the dielectric constant of the medium⁸. When the percentage of 1,4-dioxane is varied in the mixed solvent the dielectric constant is also varied which in turn varies the values of the molar absorptivity. Therefore, by changing the percentage of 1,4-dioxane, it was observed that the value of molar absorptivity of Fe^{III}-charge transfer complex of 5-sulphosalicylic acid (Table 1) and 5-chlorosalicylic acid (Table 2) also changes.

Therefore, for the determination of stability constant in medium of different amount of 1,4-dioxane same value of molar absorptivity can not be used. Hence, the simultaneous determination of molar absorptivity and stability constant of charge transfer complex in different percentage of 1,4-dioxane, is advantageous.

Taking salicylic acid as reference ligand for comparing of a λ_{max} of 1 : 1 complex for the complex with Fe^{III},

Table 1. The comparative values of stability constant (K) and molar absorptivity (ϵ_0) obtained by this method and that obtained from Frank and Ostwald method for (1 : 1) Fe^{III} -5-SSA complex at different proportion of 1,4-dioxane in solvent mixture. The $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 496.4$

Sl. No.	% of 1,4-Dioxane	Medium pH range 2.35 ± 0.05	Frank and Ostwald method			Computational (Iteration) method		
			k	$\log k$	$\epsilon_0 \times 10^3$	$k \times 10^3$	$\log k$	$\epsilon_0 \times 10^3$
1.	0	Acidic	6473	3.81	1.93	9.38	3.97	1.33
2.	5	Acidic	6787	3.83	1.96	9.93	3.99	1.35
3.	10	Acidic	7778	3.89	2.14	11.61	4.06	1.43
4.	15	Acidic	8890	3.94	2.30	13.02	4.11	1.56
5.	20	Acidic	9259	3.96	2.37	13.77	4.13	1.61

Table 2. The comparative values of stability constant (K) and molar absorptivity (ϵ_0) obtained by this method and that obtained from Frank and Ostwald method for (1 : 1) Fe^{III} -5-Cl-SA complex at different proportion of 1,4-dioxane in solvent mixture. The $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 504.8$

Sl. No.	% of 1,4-Dioxane	Medium pH range 2.35 ± 0.05	Frank and Ostwald method			Computational (Iteration) method		
			k	$\log k$	$\epsilon_0 \times 10^3$	$k \times 10^3$	$\log k$	$\epsilon_0 \times 10^3$
1.	0	Acidic	7272	3.86	2.29	10.43	4.04	1.53
2.	5	Acidic	8518	3.93	2.34	12.79	4.10	1.56
3.	10	Acidic	9318	3.96	2.38	13.59	4.13	1.63
4.	15	Acidic	9642	3.98	2.59	14.79	4.17	1.69
5.	20	Acidic	9851	4.00	2.89	15.63	4.19	1.82

λ_{max} was recorded as 500 nm. The λ_{max} Fe^{III} -5-sulphosalicylic acid complex is at 496.4 nm which shows a hypsochromic shift and that of Fe^{III} -5-chlorosalicylic acid complex has λ_{max} at 504.8 nm which indicate a bathochromic shift.

Experimental

All chemicals such as ferric chloride (BDH), 5-sulphosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid (E. Merck), 1,4-dioxane (E. Merck) were of analytical grade (AR grade), used without any further purification. For making mixed solvent double distilled water was used. Four mixed solvents were prepared in which the proportion of 1,4-dioxane was varied as 5, 10, 15 and 20%.

The solvent mixtures were kept for two hours before use. All the standard solutions of Fe^{III} -ion and ligand solutions were prepared in these mixed solvents.

The composition of the complex formed by Fe^{III} with 5-sulphosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid was determined in the acid range of the pH using Job's method of continuous variations (Figs. 1 and 2). In all the mixed solvent percentages the complex formed in the pH range 1 to 3 was found to be 1 : 1.

The variation in values of molar absorptivity with the percentage of 1,4-dioxane in mixed solvent is given for Fe^{III} with 5-sulphosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid 1 : 1 complex in Figs. 3 and 4 respectively.

Fig. 1. Job's method : Fe^{III} -5-SSA complexes.

Fig. 2. Job's method : Fe^{III} -5-Cl-SA complexes.

Fig. 3. The variation in values of molar absorptivity with the percentage of 1,4-dioxane in mixed solvent : Fe^{III}-5-SSA complexes.

Fig. 4. The variation in values of molar absorptivity with the percentage of 1,4-dioxane in mixed solvent : Fe^{III}-5-Cl-SA complexes.

A double beam UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Systronics Model 2202) with 1 cm quartz cells were used for all absorbance measurements. On recording the spectra in the visible range the λ_{max} were observed at 496.4 nm and 504.8 nm respectively for the complexes and hence in subsequent measurements of the absorbance, the wavelength selected was at as 496.6 nm and 504.8 nm respectively.

Conclusion

We have studied the effect of solvent on the stability constant of 1 : 1 complex formed by Fe^{III} with 5-sulphosalicylic acid and 5-chlorosalicylic acid at pH 2.35 \pm 0.05. In acidic medium, the color of the solution becomes violet due to the formation of a stable charge transfer complex between the metal ion and respective ligands. The stability constant and molar absorptivity were determined simultaneously with a novel graphical-cum-computational method in different composition of water-1,4-dioxane mixed solvent.

Taking salicylic acid as reference ligand, the follow-

ing substitution effects were observed in λ_{max} of 1 : 1 complex :

Fe^{III}-5-SSA hypsochromic shift

Fe^{III}-5-Cl-SA bathochromic shift

The stability constant and molar absorptivity values increases with increase in the percentage of 1,4-dioxane in mixed solvent in case of both the complexes.

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